

RECENT TRENDS IN CONDITION ASSESSMENT OF INDUCTION MOTOR DRIVES

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ABSTRACT

The present paper highlights some of the current practices being adopted by technologists and industrialists to pre assess catastrophic faults in an induction motor drive. An overview of modern techniques such as DSP based technique like Fourier transforms, Short time Fourier transform (STFT), Wigner-Ville Distribution (WVD), Wavelet Transforms, Park Vector Technique, Gabor Transforms etc. has been presented in this paper. It has been observed that real time implementation of this process undoubtedly involves expensive tools, yet it is cost effective in the long-run resulting in savings and prevention of electrical drive system faults. The pre-fault warning & timely detection of electric drive system faults also help in prolonged life and reliability of the drive which facilitates reduction of energy and capital loss.

KEYWORDS: Induction Motor, DSP, Fault Detection, Sensors

INTRODUCTION

A large number of Induction motor drives has a direct influence on production in many industrial applications. The Induction motor drives can be energized from constant frequency sinusoidal power supplies or from adjustable frequency, power supplies. However, Induction motors are susceptible to many types of faults, especially when supplied by the variable ac power supplies. This is due to the extra voltage stresses on the stator windings, the resulting induced bearing currents, and the high-frequency stator current components. In addition, motor over voltages can occur because of the length of cable connections between a motor and an ac drive. This fact gave rise to requirement of higher reliability and it has also evoked the research activity in the field of condition monitoring and fault diagnosis of induction machines. Figure 1 shows a block diagram of the general approach to On-line condition monitoring process which takes measurements while a machine is operating, to determine if a fault exists [1]. Starting from the left, common motor faults are shown. Different types of sensors can be used to measure signals to detect these faults. Various signal processing techniques can be applied to the sensor signals to extract particular features which are sensitive to the presence of faults. Finally, in the fault detection stage, a decision needs to be made as to whether a fault exists or not. The results of the 1982 survey [1,2,3] on the reliability of motors in industrial and commercial installations are depicted in the Figure [2]. The survey has conducted tests on motors larger than 200H.P. and age not more than 15 years.

Bearings	Vibration	RMS	Model-Based
Stator Winding	Current	Fourier Transform	Trending
Rotor Bar	Magnetic Flux	Time-Frequency	Threshold